

NOTES

Influence of Chain Flexibility on Heat of Melting of Long Chain Molecules

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In an earlier communication¹ a statistical approach correlating the heat of melting ΔH_m of linear chain molecules with chain length, its flexibility and the corresponding torsional frequency was proposed. The following expression gave the relationship :

$$\Delta H_m = \left[\frac{(N-2)nh\omega e^{-h\omega\alpha}}{1 - e^{-h\omega\alpha}} + fn(N-2) \Delta U \right] \left[\frac{V_0}{V} - \left(\frac{V-V_0}{V} \right) \delta \right] + \frac{3}{2} NRT_m \left(\frac{V-V_0}{V} \right) (1-f) \dots 1.$$

where N is the number of carbon atoms, ω , the torsional frequency, f , is the flexibility,

$$\alpha = \left[\frac{1}{RT_m} - \frac{\delta}{RT_m} + \frac{\delta}{RT_m} \frac{V}{V_0} \right] \text{ and } \delta, \text{ a volume}$$

dependent parameter and rest of the symbols have their usual meaning. Two cases were considered namely for $N \gg 1$ and $f > 0$ for polymethylene, polypropene, poly 1-butene and polyvinylchloride. For shorter chains, $2 < N \leq 9$ the flexibility was assumed to be zero. The theoretical and experimental values of ΔH_m could not be compared for chains longer than $N=9$ for odd series and $N=10$ for even series due to the non-availability of experimental data.

In the present note the cases of n -alkanes and n -alkenes up to $N=20$ have been considered. Expression (1) with $f=0$ was found to be valid only for even series in case of n -alkanes. For odd series

the factor, $(1-f) = \frac{3}{4} \frac{\pi}{N} = N(1 - \frac{1}{N^2})$ was found to be satisfactory. Similarly for n -alkenes it was found that the expression $f = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\pi}{N+1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{N^2} \right)$ represents

the flexibility of compounds both even and odd number of carbon atoms. These expressions are purely empirical.

Comparison of experimental and calculated values of H_c of Melting for n -alkanes :

For calculating the theoretical values of ΔH_m , the

ratio (V_0/V) for n -alkanes has been assumed to be 0.1. Fig. 1 gives a comparison of the experimental

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

and theoretically calculated values of ΔH_m for n -alkanes². It can be seen that the agreement is

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TABLE 1—VALUES OF ΔH_m FOR *n*-ALKANES (SHORT CHAINS)

$$\omega = 270 \text{ cm}^{-1}, \alpha = \left(\frac{1}{RT_m} - \frac{\delta}{RT_m} + \frac{\delta}{RT_m} \frac{V}{V_0} \right), h\omega\alpha = 66.5/T_m, \Delta U = 600 \text{ cal per unit}$$

N	T_m °K	ΔH_m calculated cals/mole	% of torsional and thermal contributions		Exp. ΔH_m cals/mole	% error
3	85.9	705.45	1.34	98.66	840.84	-18.00
4	134.6	1486.60	2.33	97.67	1120.80	+32.60
5	143.3	1990.90	2.33	97.17	2008.08	-0.85
6	179.0	2997.40	3.26	96.74	3019.22	-0.73
7	182.5	3575.35	3.52	96.48	3338.00	+5.80
8	216.2	4854.72	3.80	96.20	4925.00	-1.40

TABLE 1—VALUES OF ΔH_m FOR *n*-ALKANES (LONG CHAINS)

$$\omega = 270 \text{ cm}^{-1}, \alpha = 1/RT_m - \delta/RT_m + \delta/RT_m(V/V_0) = 1.09/RT_m, h\omega\alpha = 66.5/T_m, \Delta U = 600 \text{ cal per unit}$$

N	T_m °K	f	ΔH_m calculated cals/mole	% of torsional, rotational and other thermal contributions			ΔH_m exper. cals/mole	% error
9	219.50	0.340	3869.0	5.67	3.36	90.97	3697.0	+4.6
10	243.30	0.0	6849.9	4.10	0.0	95.90	6864.3	-0.2
11	247.40	0.318	5486.0	5.78	2.87	91.35	5301.0	+3.5
12	263.30	0.0	8916.9	4.34	0.0	95.66	8726.1	+2.2
13	267.78	0.310	7105.0	6.10	2.62	91.28	6812.0	+4.3
14	279.02	0.0	11030.5	4.38	0.0	95.62	10772.0	+2.4
15	283.10	0.301	8704.0	6.25	2.45	91.30	8268.0	+5.2
16	291.33	0.0	13194.3	4.62	0.0	95.38	12753.0	+3.5
17	295.14	0.295	10446.0	6.25	2.30	91.45	9599.0	+8.1
18	301.33	0.0	15359.5	4.65	0.0	95.35	14780.0	+3.9
19	305.10	0.292	12117.0	6.75	2.25	91.00	10950.0	+10.6
20	309.70	0.0	17600.0	4.95	0.0	95.05	16700.0	+5.4

TABLE 2—VALUES OF ΔH_m FOR *n*-ALKENES (SHORT CHAINS)

$$\omega = 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}, h\omega\alpha = 49.2/T_m, \Delta U = 650 \text{ cal per unit}$$

N	T_m °K	Calculated value of ΔH_m cals/mole	% of torsional and thermal contributions		Exp. value of ΔH_m cal/mole	% error
3	87.91	722.6	1.61	98.39	717.7	+0.66
4	87.82	970.0	2.13	97.87	919.8	+5.4
5	107.93	1494.5	2.85	97.15	1388.0	+7.6
6	133.38	2234.0	3.32	96.68	2234.0	-4.3
7	154.29	3029.0	3.62	96.38	2964.0	+2.2
8	171.45	3848.0	3.84	96.16	3600.0	+5.1
9	191.78	4838.0	3.90	96.10	4300.0	+12.5

TABLE 2—HEATS OF MELTING OF *n*-ALKENES (LONG CHAINS)

N	T_m °K	f	Calculated value of ΔH_m cal/mole	% of torsional, rotational and thermal contributions			Exp. value of ΔH_m cal/mole	% error
10	206.88	0.550	3015	8.13	8.62	83.25	3300	-8.6
11	223.98	0.546	3608	8.30	8.05	83.65	4061	-11.1
12	237.92	0.542	4251	8.47	7.55	83.98	4758	-10.7
13	250.08	0.539	4921	8.60	7.27	84.13	5200	-7.3
14	260.30	0.536	5465	8.55	6.95	84.50	5600	-2.3
15	269.42	0.533	6036	8.90	6.78	84.32	6900	-12.5
16	277.50	0.532	6641	8.98	6.64	84.38	7216	-7.9
17	284.40	0.529	7235	9.00	6.48	84.52	7500	-3.5
18	290.80	0.528	7883	8.95	6.35	84.70	7800	+1.8
19	296.60	0.526	8581	9.55	6.17	84.28	8000	+7.3
20	301.80	0.525	9162	9.65	6.10	84.25	8200	+11.7

fair. The maximum error is found to be approximately 5% for even series and about 10% for odd series. The average error is found to be 4.47% for alkanes and 0.69% for alkenes.

Comparison of experimental and calculated values of Heats of Melting for n-alkenes :

For comparing the heats of melting for *n*-alkenes no distinction has been made for the flexibility of long chains having odd and even number of carbon atoms for calculating the values of heats of melting. These values show good agreement with experimental⁸ values (Fig. 2). The data shows that the per cent error is both negative and positive at random.

From the break up of the contributions towards ΔH_m it can be seen that the maximum contribution arises out of the partition function due to the introduction of gas like holes and is approximately 80% of the total value. Moreover, the gas like partition function becomes asymptotic beyond a certain value of *N*, the number of carbon atoms. The stepwise variation observed in the values of ΔH_m in the odd-even numbered carbon atom chains is reproduced.

References

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Deelectronation Mechanism of Hydrazine by Mn^{3+}

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OXIDATION of hydrazine by different monodeelectronators¹⁻⁴ has been studied extensively, but with contradictory reports. The oxidative mechanism of most of the deelectronations has been reported to vary with the working conditions like the concentration of acid, order of addition of reagents and temperature etc.

While Huang and Spence⁵ reported Mo(VI) acting as dideelectronator in pH range 1.2-3.2 in the oxidation of hydrazine, Mishra and Sinha¹ established Mo(VI) as the monodeelectronator in 1*N* H₂SO₄ medium. Prasad and Kumar² reported V(V) acting as monodeelectronator in the oxidation of hydrazine, when V(V) solution was added to

hydrazine and they proposed intermediates, N₂H₃, N₂H₂ and N₂H. Contradictory results have been reported in the oxidations of hydrazine by monodeelectronators^{3,4}, Ce(IV) and Fe(CN)₆³⁻.

Mn³⁺ is found to be very strong deelectronator⁶ and has been used for kinetic studies of the oxidations of hydroxylamine^{7a} and hydrazine^{7b} in perchloric acid. In the present communication we have reported the studies on oxidation of hydrazine in 9*N* H₂SO₄ with Mn³⁺. It is found that hydrazine undergoes four electron change in one electron steps.

Experimental

Manganous sulphate, potassium permanganate, sulphuric acid and hydrazine sulphate used in this study were B. D. H. Analar.

Mn³⁺ was prepared by the oxidation of Mn²⁺ by MnO₄⁻ in acidic medium as described by Ubbelohde⁸. In 9*N* H₂SO₄ Mn³⁺ was quite stable for 24 hours and was standardised with a solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate (B. D. H. Analar). For oxidation study, the titration was broken up in different independent stages as described by Gyani and Prasad⁹. A number of cells were arranged in series. In each cell equal amount of M/40 reductant (10 ml) and increasing amounts of oxidant (M/10) were added.

The potential of each cell was recorded after 1 hour, 3 hours, 6 hours, 9 hours and 12 hours of the addition of oxidant. The readings taken after 1 hour and 12 hours and after heating the mixture for 2 hours at 90° and subsequent cooling for 24 hours are given in Table 1. The exact volume of oxidant at which sharp inflexions (Fig. 1) were observed are recorded in Table 1.

Fig. 1